

Adversarial Confusion Attacks: Disrupting Multimodal LLMs

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Abstract

We introduce *adversarial confusion attacks* as a new class of threats against multimodal large language models (MLLMs). Unlike jailbreaks or targeted misclassification, the objective is to induce *systematic malfunction*: incoherent or confidently wrong text. The long-term goal is to craft adversarial confusion images that can be embedded into websites (e.g., as background elements), thereby preventing MLLM-powered AI Agents from operating on those sites. In this paper we present preliminary results limited to the direct MLLM setting, where adversarial images are submitted as model inputs. Our method maximizes next-token entropy under *expectation over transformations* (EoT) and a small ensemble of open-source MLLMs. The attack transfers to some proprietary models (GPT-5-high, GPT-o3 and Amazon Nova Pro), which produce structurally coherent hallucinations. This is a work in progress; code will be released with the final version.

1 Introduction

Multimodal large language models (MLLMs) are increasingly used as a core of AI Agents that can perform complex tasks on webpages and apps running on end-user devices. Prior defenses and attacks predominantly target content steering or targeted misclassification (Aichberger et al., 2025). We focus on a complementary risk: *confusion as a goal*.

In an adversarial confusion attack, the adversary seeks to induce incoherent or confidently wrong outputs, thereby degrading the perception of an MLLM-based Agent and ultimately preventing it from reliably operating on a targeted website. The attacker is assumed to control the visual environment (e.g., webpage backgrounds, embedded images, UI patches), but not the text prompts or the internal decoding strategies of the model.

In this preliminary work we restrict to the model-only setting: adversarial images are supplied di-

rectly to MLLMs. We optimize perturbations with a simple principle: *maximize next-token entropy* averaged across an ensemble of open-source MLLMs. To improve robustness and transferability, we employ *Expectation over Transformations* (EoT) (Athalye et al., 2018), i.e., we optimize perturbations over a small distribution of differentiable input transforms. Proprietary models are evaluated strictly in a **black-box** manner; they are never used for adversarial training, fine-tuning, or gradient access.

This work complements existing literature on adversarial examples by making *confusion* the explicit objective. Recent work has demonstrated adversarial attacks on MLLMs (Rahmatullaev et al., 2025), transferable black-box perturbations against proprietary MLLMs such as GPT-4o (Hu et al., 2025), universal perturbations (Moosavi-Dezfooli et al., 2017), ensemble scaling laws that govern black-box adversarial effectiveness (Liu et al., 2025), and theoretical accounts of how internal representations might relate to robustness (Huh et al., 2024). Our empirical results suggest that entropy-driven EoT training on even a modest surrogate ensemble suffices to transfer to leading proprietary models like GPT-5.

(a) **GPT-5-high**: Example of a structured hallucination induced by an adversarial input. By contrast, Gemini 3 (“Oceanreef”) resists the same perturbation and classifies the image as noise, which is the default behavior of MLLMs resistant to attack.

(b) **GPT-o3**: Structured hallucination produced by the adversarial input. In contrast, Gemini 2.5-pro resists and labels the same input as AI-generated art or noise.

(c) **Clean base image**. Screenshot of a webpage (original resolution 1900 × 1000 pixels).

(d) **Adversarial image**. Same base screenshot with entropy-max adversarial perturbation. Image shown has been downsampled and corrupted to prevent reuse in adversarial attacks.

Figure 1: **Black-box transfer**: proprietary model outputs for adversarial inputs. The third row shows adversarial image next to its clean base.

2 Method

Setup. Let $x \in [0, 1]^{3 \times H \times W}$ be an input image and let $\mathcal{R} \subseteq \{1, \dots, H\} \times \{1, \dots, W\}$ denote an optional patch region. We optimize an additive perturbation δ applied either on \mathcal{R} (patch) or on the whole image (full-frame). With a binary mask $M \in \{0, 1\}^{H \times W}$ that is 1 on \mathcal{R} and 0 elsewhere, the perturbed image is

$$x_\delta = \Pi_{[0,1]}(x + \delta \odot M), \quad \|\delta\|_\infty \leq \varepsilon,$$

where $\Pi_{[0,1]}$ clips to the valid pixel range and ε bounds perceptibility.

Ensemble of MLLMs. We attack an ensemble $\mathcal{E} = \{(f_j, w_j)\}_{j=1}^J$ of open-source Multimodal LLMs (Liu et al., 2025) with nonnegative weights w_j (normalized so $\sum_j w_j = 1$). Each model f_j is queried with a fixed text prompt t and a model-specific preprocessing pipeline $\Phi_j(\cdot)$.

Expectation over transformations (EoT). To encourage robustness and transfer, we employ EoT (Athalye et al., 2018) over a distribution \mathcal{T} of differentiable transforms g (e.g., geometric jitter). The transformed adversarial input is $g(x_\delta)$.

Top- K entropy objective. For model f_j , let the next-token logits over vocabulary \mathcal{V} be

$$Z_j = f_j(\Phi_j(g(x_\delta), t)) \in \mathbb{R}^{T \times |\mathcal{V}|}, \quad z_j = Z_j[\tau_j, :],$$

where τ_j indexes the last attended position (end of the prompt). With temperature $T_e > 0$, the (optionally top- K) probabilities are

$$p_j = \text{softmax}(z_j/T_e),$$

and we use Shannon entropy

$$H(p_j) = - \sum_{v \in \mathcal{V}} p_j(v) \log p_j(v).$$

(for top- K , z_j is truncated to its K largest logits before the softmax.)

Attack objective. We induce confusion by maximizing expected next-token entropy across transforms and models:

$$\max_{\|\delta\|_\infty \leq \varepsilon} \mathbb{E}_{g \sim \mathcal{T}} \left[\sum_{j=1}^J w_j H(p_j(g(x_\delta), t)) \right],$$

equivalently minimizing

$$\mathcal{L}(\delta) = - \mathbb{E}_{g \sim \mathcal{T}} \left[\sum_{j=1}^J w_j H(p_j(g(x_\delta), t)) \right].$$

Optimization and projection. We perform projected gradient ascent (PGD-style, implemented with Adam; (Madry et al., 2017)) on δ :

$$\delta \leftarrow \Pi_{\|\cdot\|_\infty \leq \varepsilon}(\delta + \eta \nabla_\delta \mathcal{L}(\delta)),$$

with per-step clipping of x_δ to $[0, 1]$ and gradient averaging over $g \sim \mathcal{T}$.

3 Experiments

Surrogates and black-box targets. We optimize against a small surrogate ensemble of open MLLMs (e.g., Qwen2.5-VL, LLaVA-1.5, GLM-4.1V). We then evaluate transfer to proprietary models via the LMSys Chat Arena web interface (GPT-5-high, GPT-o3, GPT-4o, LLaMA-4-Scout, Qwen3-VL, Mistral-medium, Amazon-Nova-Pro, Grok-4, Gemini 2.0, 2.5 and 3.0 (“Oceanreef”)).

Qualitative results. We illustrate core findings in Figure 1. Subfigure (a) shows GPT-5-high generating a coherent but incorrect hallucination on an adversarial input, while subfigure (b) demonstrates a similar effect on GPT-o3. Comparable behavior was also observed for Amazon Nova Pro. By contrast, Gemini 2.5 and Gemini 3 (“Oceanreef”) classify the same adversarial image as visual noise or static, which is the default behavior of models resistant to attack.

Subfigures (c) and (d) compare the clean base image to its entropy-maximized adversarial counterpart. Additional adversarial examples are collected in Figure 3, illustrating the diversity of entropy-maximized perturbations. These examples, however, were generated without an ensemble and therefore do not achieve the same level of transferability as our main results.

The training results are visualized in Figure 2, which reports entropy values and model outputs for clean versus adversarial inputs. Across surrogate models (e.g., AgiGemma, Qwen2.5-VL, LLaVA-1.5, GLM-4V), clean images yield low entropy and coherent webpage descriptions, while adversarial versions produce sharply higher entropy and degraded outputs.

Finally, Figure 4 demonstrates successful black-box transfers to different model families. LLaMA-4-Scout (subfigure a) produces long, structured narratives disconnected from the input; and Mistral-medium (subfigure b) unexpectedly switches languages, responding in Arabic to an English query.

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[Nadhari/AgriGemma-3n-E2B-it] CLEAN: entropy=0.2414
  → This image shows a black screen with the text "Cybernetic culture research unit" in the center.

[Nadhari/AgriGemma-3n-E2B-it] ADV: entropy=0.0400
  → This image is completely black.

--- Qwen/Qwen2.5-VL-3B-Instruct on cuda:0 ---
[Qwen/Qwen2.5-VL-3B-Instruct] CLEAN: entropy=0.6801
  → The image appears to be a screenshot of a webpage from a website called "cybernetic culture research unit," which is likely a digital archive or research platform related to cybernetics and culture.

[Qwen/Qwen2.5-VL-3B-Instruct] ADV: entropy=5.9169
  → ++++++

--- Qwen/Qwen2-VL-2B-Instruct on cuda:1 ---
[Qwen/Qwen2-VL-2B-Instruct] CLEAN: entropy=0.7316
  → The image is a screenshot of a webpage from the "Cybernetic Culture Research Unit" (CCRU) at the University of Michigan. The webpage is divided into several sections, each containing information

[Qwen/Qwen2-VL-2B-Instruct] ADV: entropy=5.9893
  → none.

--- llava-hf/llava-1.5-7b-hf on cuda:4 ---
[llava-hf/llava-1.5-7b-hf] CLEAN: entropy=0.3590
  → The image displays a computer screen with a variety of information and images. There are several text boxes and diagrams, including a large, detailed image of a person. The screen also features a menu with

[llava-hf/llava-1.5-7b-hf] ADV: entropy=2.5109
  → The image is a close-up of a computer screen, displaying a colorful and detailed scene. In the scene, there is a person standing on a surfboard, with a skateboard

--- zai-org/GLM-4.1V-9B-Base on cuda:5 ---
`generation_config` default values have been modified to match model-specific defaults: {'do_sample': True, 'temperature': 0.8, 'top_k': 2, 'top_p': 0.6, 'pad_token_id': 151329, 'eos_token_id': [151329, 151336, 151338, 151348]}. If this is not desired, please set these values explicitly.
[zai-org/GLM-4.1V-9B-Base] CLEAN: entropy=0.1218
  → <think>The image is a screenshot of a webpage titled "Cybernetic culture research unit". The page has a dark background, primarily black, with text and graphics in white, yellow, and

[zai-org/GLM-4.1V-9B-Base] ADV: entropy=1.6467
  → <think>The user wants a detailed description of the provided image. The image is a map, specifically a "Desert Map" from the game "The Legend of Zelda: A Link to the Past

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Figure 2: Training log excerpt. Response of ensemble surrogate MLLMs to a clean vs. adversarial image (denoted as ADV), along with output entropy.

Success and failure cases. Across black-box evaluations, the attack succeeded on GPT-5-high, GPT-o3, Amazon Nova Pro, LLaMA-4-Scout, and Mistral-medium. These models reliably produced structurally coherent hallucinations. By contrast, the attack did not transfer to Grok-4, Qwen3-VL, GPT-4o, or Gemini. All of these models classified the adversarial image as digital noise or static. We hypothesize that this robustness may arise from stronger input preprocessing (e.g., aggressive compression).

We emphasize that transfer in our black-box evaluations is not a mysterious discovery. Prior work indicates that (i) increasing the size and diversity of surrogate models and (ii) optimizing under an expectation-over-transforms both tend to improve

black-box transfer rates to proprietary models. In our case, we combined these two key insights.

4 Conclusion

We introduced the *adversarial confusion attack* and presented a simple entropy-maximization method with EoT that produces transferable perturbations against many popular open and proprietary MLLMs. Our experiments show that an entropy-driven objective destabilizes next-token decoding and can induce structured hallucinations, incoherent descriptions, or language shifts across multiple model families.

A core next step for this line of research is scaling the adversarial confusion attack to website-style deployments (e.g., background elements and

embedded patches; (Aichberger et al., 2025)) and performing experiments with AI Agents to quantify practical impact. Concurrently, we will also prioritize defense-focused directions, including input processing and detection, to mitigate the risks identified.

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(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

(e)

(f)

(g)

Figure 3: Examples of adversarial images produced by entropy-max with EoT on Qwen2.5-VL (single-model optimization).

(a) LLaMA-4-Scout.

(b) Mistral responded in Arabic to an English query.

Figure 4: Examples of successful black-box attacks on LLaMA-4-Scout-17B and Mistral-medium.